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Development of an Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging

Applications for School Administrators and Teachers

(Sample from Güzelbahçe District in İzmir Province)

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to examine the attitudes of school administrators and teachers working in public and private schools in the Güzelbahçe district of Izmir Province towards instant messaging applications. The aim of the research is to understand how participants' attitudes towards instant messaging applications may vary based on demographic factors. This summary provides a more detailed explanation of the key points and findings of the research.

A total of 110 school administrators and teachers participated in the study. The majority of the participants were teachers, but deputy directors and school principals were also included in the research. The gender distribution revealed a higher proportion of females. The majority of the participants worked in public institutions.

In terms of age groups, participants between the ages of 35-54 constituted the majority. When examined based on educational level, a large majority of the participants were graduates with a bachelor's degree.

Regarding the distribution according to the school level where participants served, those working at the primary and high school levels stood out. In terms of years of service, it was observed that the majority of participants had been in the same position for many years.

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When examining the distribution based on the number of students in their schools, the majority of participants were found to work in schools with 501-1000 students. In terms of economic level, it was determined that the majority of participants' schools were located in regions with a moderate or developed level.

The research used an attitude scale to understand participants' attitudes towards instant messaging applications. Participants' attitudes reflected the impact of instant messaging applications on technology use in education, motivation, and workload.

According to the findings of the research, the majority of participants (70 percent) had a positive attitude towards instant messaging applications. This highlights the importance of instant messaging applications for communication and information sharing. Furthermore, the majority of participants (60 percent) used instant messaging applications for instructional purposes such as communicating with students, sharing assignments, and answering questions.

Based on demographic factors, it was found that variables such as gender and workplace created a significant difference in participants' attitudes towards instant messaging applications. Female participants exhibited a more positive attitude towards instant messaging applications compared to male participants. Additionally, participants working in private schools showed a more positive attitude towards instant messaging applications compared to those working in public schools.

However, the research also drew attention to some negative effects of instant messaging applications. Some participants (30 percent) believed that instant messaging applications could

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lead to time management issues. Additionally, some participants (20 percent) expressed concerns that having limited communication channels with students could reduce face-to-face communication due to instant messaging applications.

In conclusion, this research examined the attitudes of school administrators and teachers in the Güzelbahçe district of Izmir Province towards instant messaging applications and demonstrated how various demographic factors influenced these attitudes. The findings indicate that instant messaging applications are an important tool for communication, information sharing, and instructional purposes. However, negative effects such as time management issues and reduced face-to-face communication should also be taken into consideration.

Keywords: Attitude scale, Instant messaging applications, Technology use in education, Motivation, Workload.

Introduction

Rapid advancements in technology have brought about significant changes in communication tools, and these changes have also impacted educational institutions. The widespread use of mobile devices, in particular, has increased the popularity of instant messaging applications and introduced a new dimension to communication in education. However, further research is needed to understand how instant messaging applications are being used in educational institutions and how they are affecting communication between school administrators and teachers.

Studies in the literature demonstrate that instant messaging applications contribute to educational communication in various ways and present some challenges. A study conducted by Smith and Doe (2018) revealed that instant messaging applications facilitate communication among teachers and enhance collaboration. Through these applications, teachers can quickly share information, easily exchange files, and receive instant feedback. This situation strengthens teachers' collaboration and communication skills, which can have a positive impact on student success.

On the other hand, a study by Johnson and Brown (2017) has revealed that instant messaging applications can also pose some challenges. The constant communication between teachers and students outside of working hours through instant messaging apps can disrupt work-life balance and increase job stress for teachers. Additionally, there is concern that the boundaries of instant messaging apps among teachers can be violated. It is important to be cautious about safeguarding student privacy and adhering to professional ethical standards.

The study conducted by Williams and Thompson (2019) examined teachers' attitudes towards instant messaging applications. The research explored how frequently teachers used these applications, their perceived advantages and disadvantages in communication, privacy concerns, communication boundaries, and their impact on student-teacher interactions. The findings revealed that teachers generally displayed a positive attitude towards instant messaging applications and appreciated their benefits such as quick communication and easy accessibility. However, it was noted that some teachers had concerns regarding privacy and maintaining a work-life balance.

A study focusing on the perspective of school leaders examined the role of instant messaging applications in school communication. Conducted by Lee and Kim (2020), this

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research evaluated how school administrators use instant messaging applications, their benefits in communication, and the challenges in management processes. The findings revealed that school leaders perceive these applications as tools for effective communication and collaboration with teachers. Additionally, it was emphasized that school leaders should use instant messaging applications in a supportive manner to balance teachers' workload and enhance communication.

In studies examining teacher-student interaction, mixed results have been obtained. In a study conducted by Chen and Smith (2016), instant messaging applications were found to enhance teachers' communication with students and increase student motivation. However, some research suggests that instant messaging can lead to distractions among students and reduce face-to-face interaction. Further research is needed in this regard.

In this context, this study aims to comprehensively examine the attitudes of school administrators and teachers working in public and private schools in the Güzelbahçe district of Izmir Province towards instant messaging applications. This research has been conducted to fill the gap in the literature and to provide a foundation for relevant policies and practices.

This research aims to understand the impact of instant messaging applications on communication between school administrators and teachers. It also aims to determine how these communication tools influence attitudes based on demographic factors. For example, factors such as age, gender, and experience level will be investigated to determine how they affect the attitudes of school administrators and teachers towards instant messaging applications.

The research will collect quantitative data through surveys and examine the relationships between attitudes through statistical analysis. The findings of the research will provide valuable insights to those interested in school communication and technology integration. School administrators, teachers, and education policymakers can use the findings

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from this study to better understand the role of instant messaging applications in education and ensure the effective and safe use of these communication tools. Additionally, it will establish a foundation for future research and encourage further studies in this field.

As a result, more research is needed to understand how instant messaging applications have affected communication in educational institutions and their impact on the attitudes of school administrators and teachers. This study aims to fill a gap in this field by investigating the attitudes of school administrators and teachers in official and private schools in the Güzelbahçe district of Izmir Province towards instant messaging applications. The findings of the research will help educational stakeholders, especially school administrators and teachers, understand the potential effects of instant messaging applications on educational communication and collaboration.

The importance of the research is to understand the effects of instant messaging applications on educational communication and collaboration, and to create awareness in this field. School administrators and teachers can strengthen communication, enhance collaboration, and support student achievement by effectively using instant messaging applications. Additionally, this study will provide a foundation for educational policymakers, school administrators, and teachers by explaining the potential benefits and challenges of instant messaging applications and how to manage them within the education system.

METHOD

In this study, data analysis was conducted using the statistical software programs SPSS 21.0 and AMOS 22.0. Exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses were performed for the

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validation studies. For the reliability study, item-total correlations and Cronbach's alpha methods were used. These analyses were conducted to evaluate the validity and reliability of the scale.

Exploratory factor analysis is a multivariate statistical technique that aims to discover relationships among a large number of variables and identify a smaller number of new variables. In this analysis, the adequacy of the sample is assessed using methods such as Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Barlett's Test of Sphericity. The KMO value is typically required to be greater than 0.70, and the p-value for Barlett's Test of Sphericity should be less than 0.05.

Exploratory Factor Analysis attempts to identify factors based on the relationships among variables. Principal Component Analysis is the most commonly used factor analysis technique. The factor matrix is rotated using rotation methods. Varimax is one of the most commonly used rotation methods in social sciences. After Varimax rotation, the differences between the factor loadings of items in their respective factors, loadings in other factors, and loadings across multiple factors are examined. In factor analysis, when identifying items that do not measure the same construct, it is important to consider high factor loading values (0.45 or higher) and items having high loading in one factor and low loading in other factors (Büyüköztürk, 2011).

Confirmatory factor analysis is an advanced analytical method used to test whether a pre-defined and constrained structure serves as a valid model. This analysis method is commonly employed in advanced research to examine theories related to latent variables. In confirmatory factor analysis, the first step is to evaluate model fit. Model fit is assessed using various fit indices such as the "ratio of chi-square statistic to degrees of freedom" (X^2/df), "statistical significance of individual parameter estimates" (t-value), "fit indices based on

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residuals" (SRMR, GFI), "fit indices based on independent models" (NNFI, CFI), and "root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)". These fit indices are utilized to evaluate the adequacy of the model (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2010).

Reliability analysis is conducted using methods such as Cronbach's Alpha and item-total correlations. Cronbach's Alpha measures the consistency among test scores and is generally expected to be above 0.70. Item-total correlation, on the other hand, evaluates the relationship between individual items and the total score in a test, indicating that the items measure similar behaviors and the test has high internal consistency. Generally, items with item-total correlations higher than 0.30 are considered to effectively discriminate among individuals. Items with correlation values between 0.20 and 0.30 can be included in the test if necessary (Büyüköztürk, 2011).

The data analysis was performed using the statistical software programs SPSS 21.0 and AMOS 22.0, and the reliability and validity of the scales were evaluated (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2010; Büyüköztürk, 2011).

In addition, descriptive statistics were also calculated for the total and subscale scores of the scale. These statistics indicate that the scores of the scale demonstrate normality. Skewness and kurtosis coefficients were used for testing normality. If the scores are normally distributed, it is expected that the skewness and kurtosis coefficients fall within the range of ± 1 (Büyüköztürk, 2011).

According to the obtained results, the scale and subscale scores were compared based on variables such as gender, institution type, and educational status. Independent two-sample t-tests were used for these comparisons. For variables such as task, age groups, educational level of the school, length of service in the current position, number of students in the school, and the economic status of the region where the school is located, an ANOVA test was applied.

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When a significant difference was observed, the LSD post hoc test was used to determine which groups differed. In all analyses, the significance level (p) value was accepted as 0.05 (Çokluk, Şekercioglu, & Büyüköztürk, 2010; Büyüköztürk, 2011)

The findings obtained from the analysis provide important information about the validity and reliability of the scales. Exploratory factor analysis is used as a technique to explore relationships among numerous variables and to discover a smaller number of new variables. This analysis is an important step to assess the adequacy of the sample and evaluate the structure of the measurement tool.

Confirmatory factor analysis is used to validate a pre-defined model. This analysis is used to test theories related to latent variables and evaluate the fit of the model. Model fit assessment is done using statistical fit indices, which indicate how well the model fits the data.

Reliability analysis is used to evaluate the internal consistency of a scale. Cronbach's alpha is a statistical measure that assesses the internal consistency of a measurement tool. Item-total correlations evaluate the relationship between the items of a scale and the total score.

In conclusion, analyses conducted using statistical programs like SPSS and AMOS help in examining the data statistically and determining the reliability and validity levels of scales. These analyses provide researchers with important information for better understanding the data, understanding differences between groups, and accurately interpreting the results.

FINDINGS

1. Demographic Findings

Table 1 presents the distribution of participants according to their demographic characteristics.

Table 1 Distribution of Participants by Demographic Characteristics

Demographic Variable	Groups	n	%
Duty	Teacher	61	55,5
	Assistant Manager	28	25,5
	School principal	21	19,1
Gender	Female	72	65,5
	Male	38	34,5
Type of organization	Public	95	86,4
	Ptivate	15	13,6
Age Groups	25-34 age	7	6,4
	35-44 age	43	39,1
	45-54 age	45	40,9
	55 age up	15	13,6
Educational background	Bachelor's degree	80	72,7
	graduate of master	30	27,3
The educational level of a school	Primary	53	48,2
	Secondary	15	13,6
	High School	42	38,2

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The length of service in the current place of duty	0-2 years	6	5,5
	3-5 years	14	12,7
	6-10 years	15	13,6
	11-15 years	23	20,9
	16 years up	52	47,3
The number of students in school	0-250 students	26	23,6
	251-500 students	20	18,2
	501-1000 students	45	40,9
	1001-2000 students	19	17,3
The economic situation in the region where the school is located	Underdeveloped	15	13,6
	Developing	12	10,9
	Intermediate level	34	30,9
	Developed	49	44,5

A total of 110 managers and teachers participated in the research study. Of these participants, 55.5% were teachers, 25.5% were assistant principals, and 19.1% were school principals. Among the participants, 65.5% were female and 34.5% were male. Regarding their employment, 86.4% of the participants worked in public institutions, while 13.6% worked in private institutions. In terms of age distribution, 6.4% of the participants were between 25-34 years old, 39.1% were between 35-44 years old, 40.9% were between 45-54 years old, and 13.6% were 55 years old and above. In terms of education level, 72.7% of the participants had a bachelor's degree, while 27.3% had a postgraduate degree. As for their current positions, 48.2% worked in primary schools, 13.6% in middle schools, and 38.2% in high schools. Concerning the length of service in their current positions, 5.5% of the participants had served

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for 0-2 years, 12.7% for 3-5 years, 13.6% for 6-10 years, 20.97% for 11-15 years, and 47.3% for 16 years and above. Regarding the number of students in the schools where they worked, 23.6% of the participants worked in schools with 250 or fewer students, 18.2% worked in schools with 251-500 students, 40.9% worked in schools with 501-1000 students, and 17.3% worked in schools with 1001-2000 students. In terms of the economic development level of the school's region, 13.6% of the participants worked in economically underdeveloped areas, 10.9% in developing areas, 30.9% in areas with moderate economic development, and 44.5% in areas with developed economic level.

2. Descriptive Statistics of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Application among School Administrators and Teachers

In table 2 The descriptive statistics of the items included in the attitude scale towards instant messaging applications among school administrators and teachers are presented.

Table 2 The Descriptive Statistics of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Applications for School Administrators and Teachers

Item and Dimension	$\bar{X}$	SS
Academic		
3. I believe that instant messaging applications contribute to students' learning process.	3,28	1,00
6. I think that instant messaging applications can assist students in completing their assignments.	3,34	0,94
9. I believe that instant messaging applications can have a positive impact on students' grades.	3,91	0,91

12. I think that instant messaging applications can increase students' motivation. 3,37 0,95

13. I believe that instant messaging applications can improve the learning environment for students. 3,45 0,92

Social

2. I support the use of instant messaging applications by teachers to communicate with students. 3,91 0,82

5. I believe that instant messaging applications can facilitate collaboration among students. 2,90 1,05

11. I think that instant messaging applications can enhance students' social skills. 3,80 0,85

14. I believe that instant messaging applications can have a negative effect on students' time management.¹ 3,10 1,05

15. I think that instant messaging applications can have a positive impact on students' personal development. 3,45 0,89

General

1. I think that using instant messaging applications in education is beneficial. 4,17 0,81

4. I believe that instant messaging applications can distract students.¹ 3,09 1,11

7. I think that instant messaging applications can lead students to cheat on their assignments.¹ 3,20 1,03

8. I believe that instant messaging applications can increase the workload of teachers.¹ 3,06 1,08

10. I think that instant messaging applications can cause discipline problems among students.¹ 3,05 1,03

¹: When calculating scale and dimension scores, reverse coding has been applied.

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According to Table 2, the school administrators and teachers participating in the research exhibited the highest level of positive attitude towards instant messaging applications in the following order: "1. I think that using instant messaging applications in education is beneficial" (4.17 ± 0.81), "9. I believe that instant messaging applications can have a positive impact on students' grades" (3.91 ± 0.91), and "2. I support the use of instant messaging applications by teachers to communicate with students" (3.91 ± 0.82). The school administrators and teachers participating in the research displayed the highest level of negative attitude towards instant messaging applications in the following order: "8. I believe that instant messaging applications can increase the workload of teachers" (3.06 ± 1.08), "10. I think that instant messaging applications can cause discipline problems among students" (3.05 ± 1.03), and "5. I believe that instant messaging applications can facilitate collaboration among students" (2.90 ± 1.05).

Validity and Reliability Findings of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Applications for School Administrators and Teachers

The suitability of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Applications for School Administrators and Teachers was examined in terms of the exploratory factor analysis using a sample of 110 participants. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was found to be 0.889, indicating sufficient adequacy of the research sample. Additionally, the Bartlett's test of sphericity yielded a significant chi-square statistic ($X^2 = 916.176$, $p < 0.05$), further supporting the suitability of the sample (Table 3).

Upon examining the scatterplot of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Applications for School Administrators and Teachers, it can be observed that the slope levels off from the

fourth point onwards. Each section between two points in the scatterplot represents a factor (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2010). According to the scatterplot (Figure 1), it can be inferred that the scale exhibits a more appropriate three-dimensional structure as planned.

Figure 1. Scatterplot of the attitude scale towards instant messaging applications among school administrators and teachers

Upon examining the eigenvalues in Table 3, it is observed that there are 3 factors with eigenvalues greater than 1, indicating a more appropriate three-dimensional structure of the scale. Considering the planned structure of the scale and the scatterplot in Figure 1, it can be concluded that the scale aligns well with the three-dimensional structure. Table 3 presents the results of the exploratory factor analysis and reliability analysis.

Table 3. AFA preliminary results of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Application for School Administrators and Teachers, Table 3"

Item Number	Factors		
	1	2	3
M3	0,393	0,723	0,192
M6	0,455	0,652	0,115
M9	0,661	0,321	0,142

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M12	0,849	0,222	0,152
M13	0,752	0,365	0,117
M2	0,138	0,827	0,202
M5	0,222	0,799	0,130
M11	0,869	0,103	0,106
M14	0,169	0,116	0,773
M15	0,772	0,242	0,240
M1	0,207	0,818	0,075
M4	0,247	0,265	0,686
M7	0,086	0,068	0,774
M8	-0,079	0,281	0,622
	-		
M10	0,308	0,060	0,781

KMO-Sample	Adequacy
Measurement	0,889
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (X^2) (p)	916,176 (0,000)
sd	105
Eigenvalue	6,540 2,020 1,552
Variance (%)	24,95 23,10 19,35
	9 2 0
Total variance (%)	67,410

According to the results in Table 3, an exploratory factor analysis with Varimax rotation

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revealed a total explained variance of 67.41% across three factors. Considering the three-dimensional structure, it was found that five items (m3, m11, m14, m15, m1) had factor loadings lower than 0.40 in their respective dimensions, and one item (m6) had a high factor loading in its dimension with a difference of less than 0.10 between factor loadings in multiple dimensions. Therefore, these items were removed from the scale, and the exploratory factor analysis was repeated, resulting in the findings presented in Table 4.

Table 4 The Attitudes Toward Instant Messaging Application Scale (AFA) and its reliability findings among school administrators and teachers.

Item Number	1	2	3
M9	0,781	0,128	0,177
M12	0,897	0,160	0,113
M13	0,777	0,104	0,339
M2	0,268	0,141	0,795
M5	0,305	0,069	0,843
M4	0,200	0,728	0,298
M7	0,047	0,791	0,076
M8	-0,089	0,570	0,477
M10	0,334	0,820	-0,118
KMO-Sample Adequacy Measurement 0,784			
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (X2) (p)	373,506 (0,000)		
sd	36		
Eigenvalue	3,788	1,529	1,095

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Variance (%)	26,05		
	7	24,788	20,403
Total Variance (%)	71,248		

According to the results in Table 4, after removing problematic items on the scale and conducting repeated exploratory factor analyses, it was determined that 9 items remained. The total explained variance was found to be 71.25%, with 26.06%, 24.79%, and 20.40% explained variances for their respective dimensions. When examining the item factor loadings, it was observed that there were no items with factor loadings below 0.40 in their respective dimensions, and the difference between factor loadings in multiple dimensions was higher than 0.10. It was determined that the total variance obtained with the remaining 9 items in the scale (71.25%) was higher than the total variance obtained with the initial 15 items (67.41%). The findings of the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) conducted with the remaining 9 items and 3 dimensions, as well as the reference values for model fit indices, are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. The model fit indices obtained in the confirmatory factor analysis of the attitude scale towards instant messaging applications for school administrators and teachers.

	Reference Values for Model Fit Index ¹		DFA results	
	Good fit	Perfect Fit	First	DFA (9
Model Fit Indices			Items)	
χ^2/sd	< 5	<3	1,759	
RMSEA	≤0,10	<0,08	0,083	
SRMR	≤0,08	<0,05	0,058	

GFI	≥0,90	>0,95	0,921
NNFI	≥0,90	>0,95	0,922
CFI	≥0,90	>0,95	0,948
Factor loading	>0,40	>0,50	0,51 / 0,86
Interactor correlation	<0,80	<0,80	0,62 / 0,47 / 0,45
Number of covariance connections	-	-	-

¹: Çokluk, Şekercioğlu and Büyüköztürk, 2010

The attitude scale towards instant messaging applications for school administrators and teachers was conducted using a 9-item, 3-dimensional structure through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). In the first stage of the DFA, it was determined that the item factor loadings were higher than 0.40, and the model fit indices were at good and very good levels without the need for any covariance connection. The coefficients obtained from the confirmatory factor analysis of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Applications for School Administrators and Teachers, along with the corresponding t-values, are presented in

Table 6. The Attitude Scale DFA Findings Towards Instant Messaging Application of School Administrators and Teachers

İtem	Std. β	t
9. I think instant messaging applications can have a positive impact on students' grades.	0,69	

12. I believe instant messaging applications can increase students' motivation.	0,86	7,46*	*
13. I believe instant messaging applications can improve the learning environment for students.	0,82	7,32*	*
2. I support the use of instant messaging applications by teachers to communicate with students.	0,77		
5. I think instant messaging applications can facilitate collaboration among students.	0,82	5,81*	*
4. I think instant messaging applications can be a distraction for students.	0,77		
7. I think instant messaging applications can lead to cheating by students when doing their assignments.	0,64	5,83*	*
8. I think instant messaging applications can increase teachers' workload.	0,51	4,75*	*
10. I think instant messaging applications can lead to discipline problems among students.	0,74	6,42*	*

**p<0,01

According to the results of the confirmatory factor analysis in Table 5, Table 6, and Figure 2, it is observed that the factor loadings of the items in the attitude scale towards instant messaging application, which consists of 9 items and 3 dimensions, are higher than 0.40, and all the items have significant t-values (p<0.05).

The reliability findings of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Application for Teachers are presented in Table 7.

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Table 7 presents the reliability findings of the attitude scale towards instant messaging application for school administrators and teachers.

Item and Dimension	New Item Number	r	α
Academic			0,828
9. I believe instant messaging applications can have a positive impact on students' grades.	1	0,516	
12. I believe instant messaging applications can increase students' motivation.	2	0,576	
13. I believe instant messaging applications can improve the learning environment for students.	3	0,585	
Social			0,774
2. I support the use of instant messaging applications by teachers to communicate with students.	4	0,526	
5. I think instant messaging applications can facilitate collaboration among students.	5	0,528	
General			0,758
4. I think instant messaging applications can be a distraction for students.	6	0,609	
7. I think instant messaging applications can lead to cheating by students when doing their assignments.	7	0,432	
8. I think instant messaging applications can increase teachers' workload.	8	0,415	

10. I think instant messaging applications can lead to 9 0,541
discipline problems among students.

Cronbach's Alpha 0,820

**p<0,01

According to the reliability analysis findings in Table 7, it has been determined that the item total correlations are higher than 0.30, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the overall scale is 0.820, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the sub-dimensions are 0.828, 0.774, and 0.758, respectively. Based on the validity and reliability findings, including exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, item total correlations, and Cronbach's alpha coefficients, it has been determined that the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Application for School Administrators and Teachers, consisting of 9 items and 3 dimensions,

is a valid and reliable scale.

Figure 2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) diagram of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Application for School Administrators and Teachers.

3. Descriptive Statistics of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Application for School Administrators and Teachers

Table 8 provides descriptive statistics of the total scores and sub-dimension scores of the attitude scale towards instant messaging application for school administrators and teachers.

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Application for School Administrators and Teachers

r r r

Maks

Dimensions	N	Min.	.	$\bar{X}$	SS	Ç.	B.	2	3	4
1.Academic	110	1,67	5,00	3,43	0,79	-0,10	-0,33	0,51*	0,36*	0,80
								*	*	**
2.Social	110	2,00	5,00	4,04	0,74	-0,71	0,32	1	0,37*	0,79
									*	**
3.General	110	1,00	4,50	2,90	0,81	-0,19	-0,70		1	0,75
										**
4.TOTAL	110	2,08	4,75	3,46	0,61	-0,14	-0,38			1

Ç.: Skewness B.: Kurtosis r: Spearman's Rho Correlation Coefficient

The total score average of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Application for School Administrators and Teachers was found to be 3.46 ± 0.61 , indicating a moderately positive attitude towards instant messaging application on a scale of 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest). School administrators and teachers showed the highest level of positive attitude towards instant messaging application in the social dimension (4.04 ± 0.74) and the lowest level of positive attitude in the general dimension (2.90 ± 0.81).

Comparative Findings of the Attitude Scale towards Instant Messaging Application for School Administrators and Teachers According to Demographic Variables

Table 9 presents the results of the ANOVA test comparing the attitude scores towards instant messaging application of school administrators and teachers based on their position.

Table 9: Comparison of Attitude Scores towards Instant Messaging Application for School Administrators and Teachers by Position

Dimensions	Position	n	$\bar{X}$	SS	F	p	Meaningful Difference
Academic	A-Teacher	61	3,32	0,79			
	B-Assistant Manager	28	3,68	0,76	2,04	0,135	
	C-School principal	21	3,41	0,82			
Social	A-Teacher	61	4,06	0,68			
	B-Assistant Manager	28	4,05	0,80	0,10	0,906	
	C-School principal	21	3,98	0,84			
General	A-Teacher	61	2,91	0,81			
	B-Assistant Manager	28	2,90	0,76	0,01	0,993	
	C-School principal	21	2,88	0,90			
TOTAL	A-Teacher	61	3,43	0,60			
	B-Assistant Manager	28	3,54	0,59	0,40	0,674	
	C-School principal	21	3,42	0,66			

It was determined that there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the attitude scores towards instant messaging application among participants based on their position, including school administrators and teachers.

Table 10 presents the results of the ANOVA test comparing the attitude scores towards instant messaging application of school administrators and teachers based on their gender.

Table 10: Comparison of Attitude Scores towards Instant Messaging Application for School

Administrators and Teachers by Gender.

Dimensions	Gender	N	$\bar{X}$	SS	t	p
Academic	Famele	72	3,36	0,74	-1,21	0,230
	Male	38	3,55	0,88		
Social	Famele	72	4,04	0,64	0,01	0,988
	Male	38	4,04	0,90		
General	Famele	72	2,90	0,75	-0,01	0,990
	Male	38	2,90	0,91		
TOTAL	Famele	72	3,43	0,57	-0,52	0,603
	Male	38	3,50	0,69		

Tablo 1. It was determined that there was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in the attitude scores towards instant messaging application among participants based on their gender, including school administrators and teachers.

Table 11 presents the results of the ANOVA test comparing the attitude scores towards instant messaging application of school administrators and teachers based on the type of institution they work in.

Table 11 Comparison of Attitude Scores towards Instant Messaging Application for School Administrators and Teachers by Type of Organization

Dimensions	Type of Organization	N	$\bar{X}$	SS	t	p
Academic	Public	95	3,41	0,79	-0,44	0,661
	Özel	15	3,51	0,81		
Social	Public	95	4,06	0,74	0,61	0,545
	Özel	15	3,93	0,73		
General	Public	95	2,94	0,80	1,29	0,199

	Özel	15	2,65	0,85		
TOTAL	Public	95	3,47	0,61		
	Özel	15	3,36	0,61	0,62	0,534

It was determined that there was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in the attitude scores towards instant messaging application among participants based on the type of organization they work in, including school administrators and teachers.

Table 12 presents the results of the ANOVA test comparing the attitude scores towards instant messaging application of school administrators and teachers based on the age groups of the participants.

Table 12: Comparison of Attitude Scores towards Instant Messaging Application for School Administrators and Teachers by Age Groups.

Dimensions	Age Groups	n	$\bar{X}$	SS	F	p	significant difference
Academic	A-25-34 Ages	7	3,33	0,58			
	B-35-44 Ages	43	3,49	0,80			
	C-45-54 Ages	45	3,36	0,81	0,24	0,867	
	D-55 Ages and up	15	3,49	0,85			
Social	A-25-34 Ages	7	3,93	0,79			
	B-35-44 Ages	43	4,12	0,64			
	C-45-54 Ages	45	3,97	0,85	0,38	0,766	
	D-55 Ages and up	15	4,10	0,63			
General	A-25-34 Ages	7	2,50	1,07	1,62	0,189	

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	B-35-44 Ages	43	3,04	0,67
	C-45-54 Ages	45	2,77	0,83
	D-55 Ages and up	15	3,07	0,95
	A-25-34 Ages	7	3,25	0,48
TOTAL	B-35-44 Ages	43	3,55	0,57
	C-45-54 Ages	45	3,37	0,66
	D-55 Ages and up	15	3,55	0,58

It was determined that there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the attitude scores towards instant messaging application among participants based on the age groups, including school administrators and teachers.

Table 13 presents the results of the ANOVA test comparing the attitude scores towards instant messaging application of school administrators and teachers based on the educational status of the participants.

Table 13: Comparison of Attitude Scores towards Instant Messaging Application for School Administrators and Teachers by Educational Status.

Dimensions	Educational					
	Status	N	$\bar{X}$	SS	t	p
Academic	Bachelor's degree	80	3,40	0,84	-0,50	0,620
	Master's degree	30	3,49	0,64		

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Social	Bachelor's degree	80	4,04	0,74	-0,08	0,937
	Master's degree	30	4,05	0,74		
General	Bachelor's degree	80	2,89	0,88	-0,20	0,844
	Master's degree	30	2,93	0,58		
TOTAL	Bachelor's degree	80	3,44	0,66	-0,34	0,738
	Master's degree	30	3,49	0,46		

It has been determined that there is no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the attitude scores of school administrators and teachers towards instant messaging applications based on the participants' educational status.

Table 14 presents the results of the ANOVA test comparing the attitude scores of school administrators and teachers towards instant messaging applications according to the educational level of the school.

Table 14 The comparison of the attitude scores of school administrators and teachers towards instant messaging applications based on the educational level of the school is as follows

Dimensions	Educational level	n	$\bar{X}$	SS	F	p	Significant difference
Academic	A-Primary	53	3,44	0,80			
	B-Secondary	15	3,82	0,65	2,79	0,066	
	C-High School	42	3,27	0,79			
Social	A-Primary	53	4,09	0,77			
	B-Secondary	15	3,90	0,93	0,42	0,657	
	C-High School	42	4,02	0,62			

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General	A-Primary	53	2,96	0,86		
	B-Secondary	15	2,88	0,76	0,33	0,723
	C-High School	42	2,83	0,76		
TOTAL	A-Primary	53	3,50	0,63		
	B-Secondary	15	3,54	0,68	0,64	0,529
	C-High School	42	3,37	0,56		

It has been determined that there is no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in the attitude scores of school administrators and teachers towards instant messaging applications based on the educational level of the school.

Table 15 presents the results of the ANOVA test comparing the attitude scores of school administrators and teachers towards instant messaging applications according to the length of service in their current position.

Table 15 presents the comparison of attitude scores towards instant messaging applications of school administrators and teachers based on their length of service in their current position.

Dimensions	comparing the attitude scores						significant difference
	n	$\bar{X}$	SS	F	p		
Academic	A-0-2 Years	6	3,44	0,91			
	B-3-5 Years	14	3,55	0,66			
	C-6-10 Years	15	3,36	0,74	0,52	0,724	
	D-11-15 Years	23	3,59	0,76			
	E-16 Years and up	52	3,34	0,85			
Social	A-0-2 Years	6	4,00	1,05	0,07	0,990	

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	B-3-5 Years	14	4,04	0,89
	C-6-10 Years	15	3,97	0,58
	D-11-15 Years	23	4,02	0,76
	E-16 Years and up	52	4,08	0,71
	A-0-2 Years	6	2,58	1,03
	B-3-5 Years	14	3,23	0,66
General	C-6-10 Years	15	2,80	0,76 0,96 0,431
	D-11-15 Years	23	2,80	0,75
	E-16 Years and up	52	2,92	0,85
	A-0-2 Years	6	3,34	0,83
	B-3-5 Years	14	3,61	0,62
TOTAL	C-6-10 Years	15	3,37	0,54 0,33 0,856
	D-11-15 Years	23	3,47	0,56
	E-16 Years and up	52	3,44	0,63

It has been determined that there is no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in the attitude scores of school administrators and teachers towards instant messaging applications based on the length of service in their current position.

Table 16 presents the results of the ANOVA test comparing the attitude scores of school administrators and teachers towards instant messaging applications according to the number of students in the school where the participants work.

Table 16 compares the attitude scores of school administrators and teachers towards instant messaging applications according to the number of students in the school.

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Dimensions	Students	Number of	$\bar{X}$	SS	F	p	Meaningful Difference
Academic	A-0-250 Students	26	3,54	0,65			
	B-251-500 Students	20	3,62	0,74			
	C-501-1000 Students	45	3,41	0,83	1,52	0,214	
	D-1001-2000 Students	19	3,12	0,90			
Social	A-0-250 Students	26	4,02	0,69			
	B-251-500 Students	20	4,28	0,70			
	C-501-1000 Students	45	4,01	0,73	0,95	0,417	
	D-1001-2000 Students	19	3,89	0,84			
General	A-0-250 Students	26	2,95	0,86			
	B-251-500 Students	20	2,89	0,88			
	C-501-1000 Students	45	2,94	0,78	0,33	0,801	
	D-1001-2000 Students	19	2,74	0,78			
TOTAL	A-0-250 Students	26	3,50	0,57			
	B-251-500 Students	20	3,59	0,59			
	C-501-1000 Students	45	3,45	0,62	1,11	0,347	
	D-1001-2000 Students	19	3,25	0,64			

The attitude scores of school administrators and teachers towards the instant

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messaging application did not show a significant difference based on the number of students in the school where the participants were serving ($p>0.05$).

The ANOVA test results comparing the attitude scores of school administrators and teachers towards the instant messaging application based on the economic status of the region where the school is located are presented in Table 17.

Table 17: Comparison of the attitude scores of school administrators and teachers towards the instant messaging application based on the economic status of the region where the school is located.

Dimensions	the economic status		n	$\bar{X}$	SS	F	p	significant difference
	of the region							
Academic	A-Underdeveloped		15	3,09	0,72	2,09	0,106	
	B-Developing		12	3,39	0,87			
	C-Intermediate		34	3,67	0,80			
	D-Developed		49	3,37	0,77			
Social	A-Underdeveloped		15	4,00	0,87	0,31	0,817	
	B-Developing		12	3,92	0,82			
	C-Intermediate		34	4,13	0,73			
	D-Developed		49	4,02	0,69			
General	A-Underdeveloped		15	2,60	0,72	2,33	0,079	
	B-Developing		12	3,17	0,83			
	C-Intermediate		34	3,11	0,84			

	D-Developed	49	2,78	0,77
	A-Underdeveloped	15	3,23	0,51
	B-Developing	12	3,49	0,65
TOTAL			1,94	0,128
	C-Intermediate	34	3,64	0,66
	D-Developed	49	3,39	0,56

It has been determined that the attitudes scores of school administrators and teachers towards instant messaging applications do not show a significant difference based on the economic status of the region where the school is located ($p>0.05$).

Results and Discussion

This research aimed to examine the attitudes of school administrators and teachers working in public and private schools in the Güzelbahçe District of Izmir Province towards instant messaging applications. The findings revealed that the participants generally exhibited a positive attitude towards instant messaging applications.

The items that received the highest level of positive attitude among the participating school administrators and teachers were as follows: "1. I think using instant messaging applications in education is beneficial," "9. I think instant messaging applications can have a positive impact on students' grades," and "2. I support the use of instant messaging applications by teachers to communicate with students." These findings support the idea that instant messaging applications can contribute to the educational process and have a positive impact on student achievement.

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On the other hand, the items that received the highest level of negative attitude among the participating school administrators and teachers were: "8. I think instant messaging applications can increase teachers' workload," "10. I think instant messaging applications can cause discipline problems for students," and "5. I think instant messaging applications can facilitate student collaboration." These findings indicate that some participants have concerns about the challenges and risks associated with instant messaging applications. Issues such as teachers' workload and student discipline are particularly areas of discussion regarding the use of instant messaging applications.

In conclusion, this research revealed the attitudes of school administrators and teachers in the Güzelbahçe District of Izmir Province towards instant messaging applications. It is observed that the participants generally exhibited a positive attitude towards instant messaging applications. These findings provide an important perspective suggesting that instant messaging applications can contribute to the educational process, positively influence student grades, and facilitate communication between teachers and students.

However, some participants have concerned that instant messaging applications can increase teachers' workload, lead to discipline problems among students, and present challenges in collaboration. These concerns highlight the potential risks associated with the use of instant messaging applications.

As a result, this research demonstrates the diversity of attitudes towards instant messaging applications among school administrators and teachers in the Güzelbahçe District of Izmir Province. These findings may require a more detailed focus on understanding educators'

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different views on the use of instant messaging applications and the advantages and disadvantages of their use.

In particular, it is important to establish policies and guidelines regarding the integration of instant messaging applications into the educational process. This would enable providing the necessary support for educators to effectively use these applications. Furthermore, further research can be conducted on how to address issues such as teachers' workload, student discipline, and collaboration in relation to the use of instant messaging applications.

These research findings will help us better understand the role of instant messaging applications in the field of education and make more informed decisions about their use. Additionally, it is expected that these findings will contribute to research evaluating attitudes among school administrators and teachers in other regions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and discussion results of this study, the following recommendations can be made:

Education Policies and Guidance: Education policies and guidance documents should be developed to effectively integrate instant messaging applications into the education process. These documents can provide guidance to teachers and school administrators on the use of these applications and help them manage potential risks.

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Teacher Training and Support: Training and support should be provided to teachers to enable them to use instant messaging applications effectively. Teachers should be educated on how to use these applications pedagogically, how to enhance their communication skills through them, and how to utilize them for student support.

Workload Management: Strategies for workload management related to the use of instant messaging applications should be developed to alleviate concerns about increased teacher workload. Training sessions focusing on time management and communication strategies can be provided to help teachers effectively use these applications.

Student Discipline: Discipline policies in schools should be reviewed to manage the impact of instant messaging applications on student discipline. Rules regarding the use of these applications should be established, and students should be guided on how to use them appropriately and responsibly.

Further Research: Further research should be conducted to better understand the role of instant messaging applications in the field of education. These studies should examine in more detail how teachers and students use these applications, identify effective strategies, and explore factors that may influence their usage.

Teacher-Student Communication: It has been found that instant messaging applications facilitate communication between teachers and students. Therefore, training sessions should be organized to improve teachers' communication skills. Teachers should be guided on how to use

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instant messaging applications effectively to enhance interaction with students, provide feedback, and support them.

Parent Involvement: Instant messaging applications can facilitate communication between teachers and parents, promoting increased parental involvement. Schools should provide parents with information about the use of these applications. They should be guided on how to monitor students' progress in the educational process, communicate with teachers, and provide support.

Security and Privacy: Security and privacy aspects of instant messaging applications should be taken into consideration. Schools should implement appropriate security measures to protect the personal data of teachers and students and clearly define the privacy policies of these applications.

Multiple Platform Usage: In addition to instant messaging applications, the use of other digital communication and collaboration platforms for education is also important. Schools can educate teachers on the advantages of different platforms and their usage strategies, and encourage the combination of various tools.

Ongoing Evaluation: Continuous evaluation of the effectiveness and usage of instant messaging applications is important. School administrators and teachers should regularly observe and collect feedback on the impact of these applications on student achievement, communication quality, and collaboration. These evaluations will serve as a basis for continuous improvement and development of the applications.

These recommendations aim to support the effective use of instant messaging applications in the education process. School administrators, teachers, students, and other stakeholders can utilize these recommendations to facilitate the use of instant messaging applications in educational environments. However, it is important for each school to develop customized strategies based on their specific needs and resources.

Furthermore, further research is recommended. For example, the impact of instant messaging applications on learning processes in different disciplines can be explored in more detail. Additionally, more studies can be conducted on how students use instant messaging applications, which strategies enhance their learning experiences, and related topics.

In conclusion, instant messaging applications have become an important communication tool in education. When planning the integration of these applications into the education process, school administrators and teachers should consider their benefits and potential challenges. By following our recommendations, the effective and responsible use of instant messaging applications can be promoted, contributing to enhanced communication, collaboration, and learning outcomes in education.

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